

Influence of *ortho*-Substituents on the +*M* and -*M* Effects of SCH₃ Group in Aryl Methyl Sulphides. A Study by Dipole Moments

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The dipole moments of twelve aryl methyl sulphides have been determined. The effect of mono-*ortho*- and di-*ortho*-substitution on the +*M* and -*M* effects of the SCH₃ group has been analysed by a comparison of the observed and calculated dipole moments of aryl methyl sulphides. A single substituent *ortho* to SCH₃ group is found to cause a slight steric enhancement of both the donor and acceptor resonances of SCH₃. Di-*ortho*-substitution causes steric hindrance to donor resonance but does not affect acceptor resonance.

Though the Hammett σ constant of *p*-SCH₃^{1,2} is 0.00, the group is known to function as a powerful electron-donor or electron-acceptor, when substituents of high positive or negative σ values are present in the *para*-position. The value³ of -0.604 for the σ^+ constant of SCH₃ indicates the group's ability to conjugate strongly with electron-withdrawing substituents. Dipole moment⁴⁻⁶, kinetics of H-D exchange⁷, IR⁸ and nmr⁹ spectral studies of aryl methyl studies amply indicate that the SCH₃ group conjugates equally well with electron-releasing *para*-substituents. The latter type of conjugation results from the ability of sulphur to utilise the vacant *d*-orbitals present in its valence shell. The interest to know the effect of *ortho*-substituents on both types of conjugation prompted the present study.

Results and Discussion

The effect of *ortho*-substituents on dipole moments was identified by a comparison of the observed and calculated dipole moments by vector addition of group moments. For a mono-substituted aryl methyl sulphide the dipole moment μ can be obtained by the equation¹⁰,

$$\mu^2 = \mu_1^2 + \mu_2^2 + 2\mu_1\mu_2 \cos \theta \cos \alpha \cos \beta$$

where μ_1 and μ_2 are the moments of the two substituents, θ is the angle between their axes of rotation, and α and β are the angles which these moments make with the axes of rotation (the axes are assumed to be directed to the ring). The moment of the methyl group was taken as that of toluene (0.34 D)¹¹. Similarly the moments of SCH₃, CH₃O, NH₂, NO₂, CH₃CO, Cl, Br and I groups (1.31, 1.25, 1.53, 3.95, 2.90, 1.57, 1.55 and 1.36 D)⁶ were taken as those of the corresponding substituted benzenes. The dipole angles⁵ of SCH₃, CH₃O, NH₂ and CH₃CO groups were taken as 102°, 75°, 48° and 125°, respectively.

In calculating the dipole moments of methyl *ortho*-substituted phenyl sulphides (1) from group moments, free rotation of SCH₃ was not assumed.

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a R = CH₃
b R = Cl
c R = Br
d R = I

The methoxy group in *ortho*-substituted anisoles is known to assume an orientation in which the O-methyl is away from the *o*-substituent¹². ¹³C nmr spectra indicate a similar conformation for SCH₃ in methyl *ortho*-substituted phenyl sulphides¹³. The dipole moment calculated for this conformation of 1a is 0.13 D lower than the observed moment and in the case of 1b, 1c and 1d the calculated moments are 0.29 to 0.38 D higher (Table 1). The observed differences arise due to mutual induction of the adjacent *ortho*-groups. Such is the case with a large number of *ortho*-compounds like *ortho*-dihalogenobenzenes and *ortho*-nitrohalogenobenzenes; the observed moments are consistently lower than the calculated moments except when one dipole has its positive end towards the ring and the other its positive end away from the ring¹⁴.

For the calculation of the dipole moments of methyl *para*-substituted-2-methylphenyl sulphides (sl. nos. 13-18, Table 1), the angle which the moment of 2-CH₃-1-SCH₃ moiety (2) makes with the

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TABLE 1—DIPOLE MOMENTS OF METHYL PHENYL SULPHIDES*

Sl. no.	Substituent in phenyl	μ_{obs} D	μ_{calc} D	$\Delta\mu$ D
1.	Nil	1.31	—	—
2.	2,6-Dimethyl	1.24	1.28	-0.04
3.	4-Methyl	1.49	1.42	+0.07
4.	4-Methoxy	1.98	1.86	+0.12
5.	4-Amino	2.54	2.15	+0.39
6.	4-Nitro	4.43	3.90	+0.53
7.	4-Acetyl	3.13	3.00	+0.13
8.	2-Methyl	1.13	1.00	+0.13
9.	2-Chloro	2.56	2.85	-0.29
10.	2-Bromo	2.49	2.82	-0.33
11.	2-Iodo	2.26	2.64	-0.38
12.	2-Methyl-4-chloro	1.84	—	—
13.	2-Methyl-4-bromo	1.82	1.82	0.00
14.	2,4-Dimethyl	1.33	1.22	+0.11
15.	2-Methyl-4-amino	2.37	1.96	+0.41
16.	2,5-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	1.24	1.20	+0.04
17.	2-Methyl-4-nitro	4.57	4.00	+0.57
18.	2-Methyl-4-acetyl	3.20	3.05	+0.15
19.	2,4,6-Trimethyl	1.40	1.31	+0.09
20.	4-Methoxy-2,6-dimethyl	1.99	1.83	+0.16
21.	4-Amino-2,6-dimethyl	2.35	1.98	+0.37
22.	4-Nitro-2,6-dimethyl	3.97	4.22	-0.25

*Dipole moments of compounds other than those given in Table 3 are from Ref. 5.

axis of rotation of the *para*-substituent R (assuming the axis to be directed to the *para*-substituent) was determined from the dipole moment 1.84 D of methyl 4-chloro-2-methylphenyl sulphide and the dipole moment 1.13 D of methyl 2-methylphenyl sulphide. It was calculated to be 96°. The dipole angle of 2-CH₃-1-SCH₃ moiety and not that of SCH₃ was used because of the existing mutual induction between CH₃ and SCH₃ groups. A look at the observed and calculated dipole moments of methyl *para*-substituted-2-methylphenyl sulphides (sl. nos. 14, 15, 17, 18; Table 1) reveals that both donor- and acceptor-resonances of SCH₃ are not inhibited by a single *ortho*-substituent; actually both types of resonances are slightly enhanced. Thus, for example, the $\Delta\mu$ of methyl 2-methyl-4-nitrophenyl sulphide is +0.57 D, while the same for methyl 4-nitrophenyl sulphide is +0.53 D; $\Delta\mu$ for methyl 2,4-dimethylphenyl sulphide is 0.11 D, while it is +0.07 D for methyl 4-methylphenyl sulphide. This slight increase in dipole moment caused by a single *ortho*-substituent can be due to steric enhancement of resonance¹⁶.

In calculating the dipole moments of di-*ortho*-substituted compounds (sl. nos. 19–21; Table 1) the resultant of the moments of 2,6-methyl groups was taken as the moment of a single methyl group acting towards C-4 along the 1–4 axis. In the case of methyl 4-nitro-2,6-dimethylphenyl sulphide (sl. no. 22), the di-*ortho*-substitution causes steric inhibition of conjugation of SCH₃ with the NO₂ group. The $\Delta\mu$ values of the other di-*ortho*-substituted compounds (nos. 19–21) are almost the same as those of the corresponding methyl 4-substituted phenyl sulphides, indicating that the di-*ortho*-substitution does not suppress the conjugation of the *para*-substituent with the SCH₃ group. The $-M$ effect of

SCH₃ enables sulphur to draw electrons into the vacant *d*-orbitals of its valence shell. The *d*-orbitals remain angularly undeformed, even when the SCH₃ group is twisted out of the ring plane by bulky *ortho*-substituents because when one *d*-orbital is removed from the conjugation scheme, another will take its place^{9,16}. In the case of sterically twisted anisoles and aryl methyl sulphides with OCH₃ and SCH₃ groups having $+M$ effect, increasing non-planarity of a π -electron system leads to rapid loss of conjugation, since the removal of one 2*p*-orbital of oxygen or one 3*p*-orbital of sulphur from the conjugation scheme is not compensated by another taking its place¹⁶.

Experimental

The aryl methyl sulphides were prepared by methods described earlier⁵. The physical constants of sulphides which did not find a mention in Ref. 5, are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—PHYSICAL CONSTANTS OF METHYL PHENYL SULPHIDES

Sl. no.*	Substituent in phenyl	B.p./M.p. °C	d_4^{20}	n_D^{20}
1.	2-Methyl	208–10	1.034	1.574 5
2.	2-Chloro ^a	116 5–17/15 mm		
3.	2-Bromo ^a	81–83/0.3 mm		
4.	2-Iodo ^b	132–33/9 mm		
5.	4-Chloro-2-methyl	121–22/5 mm	1.185	1.591 0
6.	4-Bromo-2-methyl	116–18/5 mm	1.456	1.615 8
7.	4-Acetyl-2-methyl	149–50/3 mm	1.123	1.611 0
8.	2-Methyl-4-nitro ^c	78–79		
9.	2,6-Dimethyl-4-nitro ^d	84–85		

*Compounds sl. nos. 1, 4, 5 and 6 showed satisfactory C and H analyses. ^aRef. 18. ^bRef. 19. ^cRef. 20. ^dRef. 21.

The dielectric constant, density and refractive index of benzene solutions were measured at 30° as described earlier¹⁷. The dielectric constant and the specific volume of benzene were taken as 2.2628 and 1.1514, respectively. The molar refraction of liquids was calculated from density and refractive index. For solids R_D was estimated from refractive index of benzene solutions. The experimental results are given in Table 3.

TABLE 3—POLARISATION DATA ON METHYL PHENYL SULPHIDES AT 30°

Sl. no	Substituent in phenyl	α	$-\beta$	∞P_s ml	R_D ml	μ D
1.	2-Methyl	1.14	0.173	70.0	44.2	1.13
2.	2-Chloro	4.59	0.343	176.3	44.2	2.56
3.	2-Bromo	3.41	0.447	174.0	49.2	2.49
4.	2-Iodo	2.36	0.531	155.8	53.1	2.26
5.	2-Methyl-4-chloro	2.25	0.294	117.7	49.2	1.84
6.	2-Methyl-4-bromo	1.77	0.458	119.3	52.1	1.82
7.	2,4-Dimethyl	1.36	0.128	85.3	49.8	1.33
8.	2-Methyl-4-nitro	12.85	0.337	474.5	53.9	4.57
9.	2-Methyl-4-acetyl	6.28	0.272	261.8	55.8	3.20
10.	2,4,6-Trimethyl	1.38	0.119	94.3	54.3	1.40
11.	2,6-Dimethyl-4-methoxy	2.48	0.202	137.0	57.5	1.99
12.	2,6-Dimethyl-4-nitro	8.62	0.320	371.5	54.7	3.97

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